

1 **Cascading effects associated with climate-change induced conifer mortality result in**
2 **enduring hot-spots of soil CO₂ emissions from mountain temperate forests**

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23

24 **Summary**

25 As a widespread phenomenon affecting terrestrial ecosystems worldwide, the extent and
26 spatio-temporal scales at which the increasing number of reported events of climate-change
27 induced tree mortality could affect the ecology and carbon (C) sink capacity of terrestrial
28 soils remains unknown. We here study how regional-scale drought-induced mortality events
29 after a very dry 2012 summer in the Carpathians mountain range (Romania), which affected
30 three of the most widely distributed conifer species: Scots pine (*Pinus silvestris*), Black pine
31 (*Pinus nigra*) and Silver fir (*Abies alba*), resulted in enduring hot-spots of CO₂ from soil
32 respiration (R_s). After 4-5 years since the main mortality event, R_s-related soil CO₂ emissions
33 under dead trees were, on average, 21% higher than those under living trees (ranging from
34 18 to 35%). These hot-spots of CO₂ were mainly resulting from the stimulation of
35 heterotrophic respiration (R_H) under dead trees. Complex cascading effects following tree
36 mortality explains the observed hot-spot of R_s and R_H. Total (R_s) and heterotrophic (R_H)-
37 related soil CO₂ emissions were strongly determined by soil environmental alterations (e.g.
38 microclimate, pH, nutrient quality/quantity or fine root demography) associated with the
39 gradual shift in aboveground vegetation dominance from conifer- to secondary successional
40 vegetation (broadleaf seedlings and grasses). On the other hand, the observed negative
41 correlation of R_H with specific length/area of fine roots (SRL/SRA), which increased around
42 dead conifers, suggest that in the long-term the resource-acquisitive strategy led by early
43 successional vegetation could gradually outcompete the hot-spot of R_H. We, therefore,
44 collected compelling evidences on how tree mortality and associated cascading effects could
45 strongly impact CO₂ emissions, alter its environmental controls and hence determine
46 ecosystem C budget and their response to climate change.

47

48 **1. Introduction**

49 The number of episodes of forest defoliation and die-off associated with climate change has
50 increased substantially during the last decades (Allen et al., 2010; Carnicer et al., 2011), and
51 it is further expected to increase even more in future decades (IPCC 2014). This increase in
52 episodes of tree mortality suggests that many tree species worldwide are experiencing their
53 survival limits under the current alterations of climate (Allen et al., 2010; Allen Craig et al.,
54 2015; Neumann et al., 2017) and subsequent increase in incidences of pests (Sangüesa-
55 Barreda et al., 2015). Since forest worldwide are of paramount importance for overall carbon
56 (C), nutrient and energy budgets (Anderegg et al., 2012), understanding physiological and
57 ecological causes of tree mortality as well as predisposition of trees to die is nowadays a hot-
58 topic that has attracted many attention and studies (McDowell et al., 2015; Rogers Brendan
59 et al., 2016; Lloret and Kitzberger, 2018).

60

61 There has been, however, identified a knowledge gap on how ecosystems are actually
62 responding to such perturbations, i.e. whether and at which extent tree mortality could affect
63 ecosystem functioning (Anderegg, Kane & Anderegg 2013). Besides altering soil abiotic
64 conditions, tree mortality limits the supply of substrate in the form of carbohydrates (e.g.
65 exudates) or nutrients (litter) demanded by belowground organs (fine roots), symbionts (e.g.
66 mycorrhiza), and soil biological communities from the rhizosphere and the soil (e.g. Högberg
67 et al., 2001; Binkley et al., 2006; Barba et al., 2016). Trees also have the capacity to modulate
68 the environmental conditions for rhizosphere heterotrophic activities, resulting in large
69 changes in the functioning (exoenzymatic activities) and diversity of the rhizosphere
70 microbial communities (Flores-Rentería et al., 2015; Flores-Rentería et al., 2016). Hence,
71 expected transformations of the landscape due to tree defoliation and mortality might be

72 associated with cascading causal-effect relations that could result in substantial changes in
73 the biological functioning of the soil system and fundamental alterations of the soil nutrient
74 and C dynamics (Flores-Rentería et al., 2018). On medium-long term, the death of trees may
75 also have critical effects over other soil functions and key soil biogeochemical cycles
76 (Rodríguez et al. 2016), resulting in chronic losses of key nutrients such as that of nitrogen
77 (N) with unknown consequences for the capacity of the systems to recover (García-Angulo
78 et al. in prep). This is because the disruption in C flow and changes in the microclimatic
79 conditions may prominently alter the composition, structure and functionality of soil
80 biological communities (Curiel Yuste, Barba et al. 2012, Avila, Gallardo et al. 2016)
81 resulting in irreversible losses in soil biodiversity and diversity of key soil functional groups
82 that sustain soil functions such as N fixation or mineralization of essential nutrients (Gómez-
83 Aparicio, Domínguez-Begines et al. 2017). Hence, given the importance of soils and their
84 biological activity for the overall ecosystem functioning and C and nutrient budgets of
85 terrestrial ecosystems (van der Heijden et al., 2008), understanding how tree mortality may
86 affect its ecology and functioning is of paramount importance to understand the potential
87 response of forest ecosystems to events of tree die-off.

88

89 The question, however, is not only understanding whether, and at which extent, tree mortality
90 will impact ecosystem functioning, but also understanding the direction an ecosystem takes
91 after such disturbance, i.e. whether ecosystems are able to absorb the perturbation or recover
92 pre-perturbation functional ranges (Moore et al. 2013; Nave et al., 2011; Barba et al., 2013;
93 Gough Christopher et al., 2013; Levy-Varon et al., 2014; Lloret et al., 2015; Avila et al.,
94 2016; Barba et al., 2016; Gazol et al., 2018). Depending on the magnitude of the mortality

95 event and/or legacies from historical management, ecosystems are able to counteract
96 potential negative effects of tree mortality and recover pre-perturbations functioning rates
97 relatively fast (Levy-Varon et al., 2014; Barba et al., 2016). This is because tree mortality,
98 depending on the ecosystem, triggers a process of recolonization by seedlings of the same
99 species (regeneration) or other species better fitted to present climatic conditions (secondary
100 succession) which slowly replaces the niche left by the vulnerable vegetation (e.g. Vayreda
101 et al., 2016; Ruiz-Benito et al., 2017). This recovery process of the ecosystems is further
102 reflected in important changes in the soil biodiversity and soil functioning (Curiel Yuste et
103 al., 2012; Lloret et al., 2015) as well as in the overall biogenic emissions from soils (Barba
104 et al., 2013; Barba et al., 2016).

105

106 Soil respiration (R_s), which represents the total biogenic CO_2 produced and emitted from
107 soils (Vargas et al., 2010), is a major ecosystem flux (Curiel Yuste et al., 2005; Davidson
108 Eric et al., 2005; Barba et al., 2018), subjected to the control of climate (soil temperature and
109 soil moisture; e.g. Curiel Yuste et al., 2003, Curiel Yuste et al. 2007), nutrient availability
110 (e.g. Janssens et al. 2010) and vegetation activity (e.g. Janssens et al., 2002; Curiel Yuste et
111 al., 2005; Tang et al., 2005; Vargas et al., 2010). Hence, understanding the key controls of
112 R_s , and how potentially tree mortality could affect it, is a matter of paramount importance to
113 further understand the capacity of terrestrial ecosystems to sequester C. Being such and
114 integrative measure of forest biological activity, understanding potential effects of tree
115 mortality on R_s is also key to mechanistically understand potential plant-soil feedbacks and
116 ecosystem responses to tree mortality. For instance, the disruption of the flow of C to
117 belowground has been directly related to almost immediate decreases in biogenic CO_2
118 emissions from soils (Högberg et al., 2001; Binkley et al., 2006; Nave et al., 2011; Levy-

119 Varon et al., 2014), due to a parallel decrease in autotrophic (fine root and mycorrhiza)
120 activity and respiration. However, studies designed to investigate in depth how effects of
121 natural events of tree die-off over soil functioning and soil resilience might be reflected in
122 soil CO₂ emissions, are still scarce.

123

124 The objective of this study was to deepen the effects of large-scale tree die-off events on soil
125 (R_s) and heterotrophic (R_H) respiration. For that, we here show a regional scale study,
126 spanning for two consecutive years (2016 and 2017), on rates of R_s in stands from the
127 Carpathians mountain range (Braşov county, Romania), where recent extreme summer
128 droughts as the one occurred in 2012, have resulted in extended mortality rates. These
129 mortality events have mainly affected conifer trees, specially Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.),
130 Silver fir (*Abies alba* Mill.), and Black pine (*Pinus nigra* Arnold). The conifers' die-off
131 observed in 2012 and estimated to extend over large areas in the forests situated at different
132 altitudes around Braşov (Forest Districts of Râşnov, Săcele, and Kronstadt), followed a
133 sequence of several extraordinary dry and hot years registered during the first decade of the
134 century (http://www.meteoromania.ro/anm/?lang=ro_ro). These affected conifers are slowly
135 replaced by autochthonous broadleaf species, especially *Quercus robur*, *Fagus sylvatica*,
136 *Fraxinus ornus*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Carpinus betulus*, *Quercus petraea* or *Acer campestre*
137 (*Table 1*). Additionally, the study collected detailed information on variables potentially
138 sensitive to tree die-off and directly/indirectly associated with R_s, e.g, soil moisture and
139 temperature, soil C and nutrients pools, R_H, and fine root biomass and morphology (e.g.
140 specific root area, SRA and root length, SRL). The ultimate aim of the study was, therefore,
141 to deepen the effects of large-scale tree die-off events on biogenic soil CO₂ emissions.

142

143 **2. Materials and Methods**

144 *2.1. Study sites*

145 We selected for this study a total number of 9 stands affected by recent tree mortality events,
146 3 from each of the studied species (Silver fir, Scots pine, and Black pine; Table 1). These
147 forests were located in the Transylvanian side of the Southern Romanian Carpathians (Braşov
148 County). As we wanted to avoid/limit as much as possible other disturbance factors (e.g.
149 management) forest were selected either in protected areas or in areas where management
150 intensity of forests has been minimal for the last decades. All stands were located in sloppy
151 terrains of the Carpathians mountain range (slopes ranging from 17 at to 37 °) in altitudes
152 between 450 (*P. nigra*) to 1250 (*A. alba*) m.a.s.l. (Table 1). Stands belonging to both pine
153 species were located between 450 and 700 m a.s.l., while the silver fir stands were situated
154 starting from \approx 800 m a.s.l) (Table 1). Both pine species are almost pure stands, that were
155 artificially regenerated 120 years ago, whereas the silver fir stands are uneven, naturally
156 regenerated, mixed stands (*Fagus sylvatica* participated up to 35% in the forest composition)
157 of approx. 160 years old. Soil type in the silver fir stands is Eutricambisols, while Rendzina
158 is the main soil type of the pine stands (Table 1). Both mean annual precipitation (MAP) and
159 mean annual temperatures (MAT) (Climate Research Unit Time Sries, CRU TS3.10; via
160 <http://climexp.knmi.nl>) were relatively low and not very variable among locations, ranging,
161 respectively from 593 to 693 mm and from 3,7 to 6,6 °C (Table 1). Our study also shows a
162 natural gradient of understorey/grassland cover from sites with very scarce understorey
163 and/or grass cover (5%) to sites with understorey and/or grass cover averaging up to 70%
164 (Table 1). The drought-induced mortality rate over 2013-2015 was estimated as 19-23% for
165 *A. alba*, 16-27% for *P. nigra* and 17-22% for *P. Sylvestris* (Table 1).

166

167 *2.2. Field measurements*

168 *2.2.1. Experimental design and tree age estimation*

169 At each of the 9 stands affected by mortality, 5 pairs of standing dead and living trees were
170 sampled (see below) along a transect perpendicular to the slope. We used a paired sampling
171 design (Bigler and Bugmann 2004), in which the selected living trees had similar size
172 (diameter at breast height, DBH), competition level, and microsite conditions with the dead
173 ones. Trees noticeably affected by biological agents (e.g. pathogens, fungus), wind, or human
174 influences were avoided during the sampling. Transects started at a random point within each
175 stand and progressed maintaining a constant altitude, and thus similar humidity conditions,
176 until the required number of trees were sampled. Distance between sampled pairs was always
177 >5 m. To establish the age of the living trees and the mortality year for the dead trees, from
178 each tree, two wood cores were extracted at breast height (1.3 m), approximately orthogonal
179 to the slope, using increment borers (Hereş et al., in preparation). At the same time, for all
180 trees, we recorded the following variables: species, status (dead, living), DBH, height and
181 crown diameters. All competitors with DBH>10 cm were inventoried over a radius of 5m,
182 together with its taxonomic identity (species), DBH and distance to the reference sampled
183 tree. We calculated a tree competition index as the sum of the diameters of all trees with
184 DBH>10 cm within 5 m radius around the reference tree. Within the same considered circle,
185 the cover degree of the understory vegetation (woody species with a DBH < 10 cm, shrubs)
186 (%) and the grass cover (%) were assessed visually.

187

188 *2.2.2. Soil respiration (R_s) measurements*

189 Starting from spring 2016, at each study site two PVC collars (10 cm in diameter, and 8 cm
190 in height) for each sampled tree were inserted into the soil to an average depth of 2.5 cm to

191 measure R_s . Collars set at this depth were stable and caused minimal disturbance to fine roots.
192 Collars were installed at around a 50 cm distance on the left and right-hand sides of each
193 trunk, in a fictitious line perpendicular to the slope. Measurements of R_s were carried out
194 with a portable infrared gas analyzer (IRGA) connected to a soil respiration chamber (EGM-
195 4 and SRC-1; PP Systems, USA) within each collar. We added the extra volume of air from
196 collars to the chamber volume of the commercial chamber (1171 cm³). The increase of CO₂
197 within the chamber was measured during 120 seconds. Soil CO₂ efflux measurements were
198 performed between 9 a.m. and 6 p.m. R_s was not measured during rainy days. When a major
199 rain event occurred (e.g., $P > 15$ mm), R_s measurements were postponed 36h in order to
200 minimize the effects of extreme precipitation on R_s .

201

202 Soil temperature (T_{soil}) was measured simultaneously with R_s , using a Soil Temperature
203 Probe (STP, PP Systems) that was inserted at 5 cm depth in soil. Soil water content (SWC)
204 was measured at 6 cm depth, using the ThetaProbe ML2X soil moisture sensor (Delta-T
205 Devices, UK) coupled to a data logger (Infield7, UMS GmBh Munchen). We performed 3
206 different measurements of soil moisture around each collar and recorded the average value
207 of them. The R_s measurements were performed within an interval of 3-4 days (for each
208 measurement campaign). Measurements were performed for different periods, resulting in 7
209 different time series: April 2016 (spring), July 2016 (summer), September 2016 (autumn),
210 November 2016 (winter), April 2017 (spring), July 2017 (summer), and October 2017
211 (autumn), covering thus all seasons. Months when the snow layer was thick, covering the
212 soil, were not considered.

213

214

215 *2.2.3. Light availability*

216 To quantify light availability, we took a hemispherical photo near every collar during the
217 2016 summer with a Nikon digital camera with fisheye lens and a self-leveling mount. Photos
218 were processed with the Winscanopy software (Regents Instruments Inc., Sainte-Foy,
219 Quebec, 2003). As a measure of light intensity, we used the total site factor (TSF) in percent
220 of above canopy light, and LAI (leaf area index).

221

222 *2.2.4. Soil sampling*

223 In Summer 2016 we collected soil samples near each PVC collar to determine: soil chemical
224 composition, soil heterotrophic activity (R_H), fine root biomass, and the different fine roots
225 functional traits (see below). We sampled three soil cores in about maximum 10 cm distance
226 around to each soil respiration collar. Soil cores were taken with a cylinder tube sampler
227 (diameter of 5 cm) on a depth of 10 cm after removing the not yet decomposed litter (O1
228 horizon) from the previous year. Afterwards, all three soil cores were merged into one single
229 composite sample related to each soil collar, put into bags and stored at cool temperature
230 (<4°C) in mobile ice boxes till further processing in the lab. A total of 180 composite soil
231 samples (9 sites x 5 couples x 2 status x 2 collars per each sampled tree) were collected.

232

233 *2.3. Laboratory analyses*

234 *2.3.1. Chemical and physical soil analysis*

235 In the laboratory, soil moisture for each soil sample was measured gravimetrically. By
236 sampling 20 g of fresh soil (avoiding stones) and drying at 105°C during 48 hours. Both
237 stones and roots (fine and coarse) were manually separated from the samples. Stones were
238 then weighted to obtain the total stone mass. The remaining soil was sieved at 2 mm, dried

239 and stored in a dark place for subsequent analyses. Water Holding Capacity (WHC) and bulk
240 density (McKenzie et al, 2014) were calculated, and soil pH was measured in distilled water
241 with a soil – H₂O ratio of 1:20 for each soil sample.

242

243 To analyze the concentrations of total organic carbon (TOC), total nitrogen (TN) and nutrient
244 content in soils, the sieved soil was grinded by hand using a mortar and divided in two
245 aliquots. One was used to calculate the nutrient content of the soil with an inductively coupled
246 plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-AES; Thermo Scientific iCAP 6500DUO,
247 ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) and the other to measure the TOC and TN
248 using an elemental analyzer (TruSpec CN, LECO, Saint Joseph, MI, USA).

249

250 *2.3.2. Root measurements*

251 Roots separated from soil samples were first washed to remove adhered soil particles and
252 sorted into two diameter classes: fine roots (diameter < 2 mm) and coarse roots
253 (diameter > 2mm). Washed fine roots were then scanned and processed with WinRHIZO
254 (Regents Instruments Inc., Quebec, Canada) to obtain fine root length, fine root diameter and
255 fine root surface area. Root components (fine and coarse roots) were dried at 65°C to a
256 constant weight for 5 days and afterwards weighed to the nearest 0.1 g. Based on these
257 measures we determined different fine root functional traits: fine root volume (FRV, cm³/g
258 soil), specific root length (SRL, ratio of fine root length to dry weight, m g⁻¹) and specific
259 root area (SRA, ratio of fine root area to dry weight, cm² g⁻¹).

260

261 *2.3.3. Soil R_H measurements under controlled conditions*

262 Soil heterotrophic respiration (R_H) was measured taking 40 g of dry, sieved soil in a sample
263 jar of 150 mL volume and rewetting it to 60 % of its WHC. Once the WHC was achieved,
264 the soil was incubated 48 hours in an environmental chamber (at 20 ° C and 80% of moisture)
265 to avoid potential anomalous pulses of CO₂ (“Birch effect”; (Birch, 1958). Afterwards, the
266 soil was incubated, controlling water content, following a temperature gradient from 5 to 35
267 ° C to cover a wide range of temperatures; R_H was measured every 10 ° C during 60 seconds
268 with an EGM-4 and the net CO₂ increase was calculated following a similar protocol to that
269 of Curiel Yuste et al. (2007) and Curiel Yuste et al. (2011). The soil heterotrophic respiration
270 used in this experiment was the averaged value of the R_H values obtained from each
271 temperature of the previous 4 measurements to cover the R_H variability in this microclimatic
272 range.

273

274 *2.4. Statistical analysis*

275 A principal component analysis (PCA) was conducted to reduce the n-dimensional of soil
276 nutrients data into two linear axes explaining the maximum amount of variance
277 (Supplementary material, Fig. S1). According to the plot of the two first PCA components of
278 the soils' elemental composition (Fig. S1), the PC1 reflects a gradient of nutrients availability
279 related with higher amounts of C, N, P, Ca, S, and Mg whereas PC2 reflects a gradient of soil
280 organic matter (SOM availability) (Fig. S1). Hence, both PC1 and PC2 were subsequently
281 used in models as a measure of the nutritional status and the substrate available in soils.

282

283 We used linear mixed-effects models (nlme R package; Pinheiro et al., 2016) to analyse the
284 influence of tree mortality and environmental data (e.g. monitored biotic and abiotic factors
285 that could potentially affect R_s) on R_s and R_H . To do so, we firstly averaged R_s values for the

286 two different PVC collars installed per each tree (see above *Soil respiration (Rs)*
287 *measurements*). As R_s and R_H data were not normally distributed, we logarithmic
288 transformed them. Linear-mixed effect models were run using two different data sets: (1)
289 seasonal data on R_s , T_{soil} , and SWC to evaluate potential effects of tree species (Silver fir,
290 Scots pine, and Black pine), time (differences among years), status (differences among dead
291 and living trees) over R_s and soil microclimate. (2) We then averaged all seasonal values
292 ($n=7$) per tree to study more in detail drivers of R_s and R_H variability.

293

294 Because our first aim was to investigate the effect of tree mortality on soil functioning, the
295 fixed part of the models included the effect of the tree vigor (healthy and dead), but also
296 accounting for other environmental factors that could explain variability in R_s and R_H (e.g.
297 soil microclimatic conditions, tree structure, SOM, soil nutritional status, fine root biomass
298 and fine root specific length/area). For all models site identification and tree species were
299 introduced as a random effect. To look for differences between vigour groups, the least-
300 squares means were analyzed applying a Tukey correction. The coefficients were estimated
301 using the restricted maximum likelihood method (REML). The residuals of the models
302 fulfilled the conditions of normality ($p > 0.05$). The selection of the final models was based
303 on the Akaike's information criterion (AIC) (i.e. minimal models with the lowest AIC).

304

305 Structural equation models (SEMs) were used to test the direct and indirect influence of both
306 biotic and abiotic factors on R_s . Since the sample size was relatively small ($n = 88$), the
307 number of predictors included in the model was thoroughly limited, as recommended by
308 Shipley (2002). Our models considered a complete set of hypothesis based on literature,
309 previous exploratory analyses (ANOVA, correlations, etc.), and our own previous experience

310 (Flores-Rentería et al., 2016; Pérez-Izquierdo et al., 2017): The model assumes that
311 aboveground vegetation structure (Size of the tree, competition with surrounding mature
312 trees, and percentage of understory and grass cover) affects both the abiotic (microclimate,
313 pH) and the biotic (root demography) environment under trees. Aboveground vegetation
314 would also affect the availability of resources (SOM quality and quantity) under trees. Both,
315 heterotrophic and total respiration (RH and Rs, respectively) will be strongly controlled by
316 changes in all these environmental factors which are ultimately controlled by aboveground
317 vegetation structure.

318

319 Several models were run and the best-fitted ones were finally selected according to the
320 covariance proximity between observed and expected data (goodness-of-fit χ^2). From the
321 general model we used multigroup SEM to test whether the studied factors were linked by
322 the same causal structure in each tree status (dead or living) and to identify the paths that did
323 not behave similarly in the two conditions (Shipley, 2002; García-Camacho et al., 2010). For
324 this analysis, we used the same hypothetical model used for each status group separately. A
325 constrained model in which all free parameters were forced to be equal across the two
326 conditions was built and contrasted with field data. Since a lack of fit was detected in the
327 fully constrained multigroup model, a series of nested models, where equality constraints
328 were removed one at a time, were developed to detect which one would significantly improve
329 the model (Shipley, 2002; García-Camacho et al., 2010). Differences in X^2 and AIC statistics
330 between the fully constrained model and the models freed from a constraint were used to test
331 for differences in parameter values between the two conditions. Standardized path
332 coefficients were estimated by using the maximum likelihood algorithm (Shipley, 2002).

333 SEM analyses were performed by using SPSS® and SPSS® AMOS 20.0 software's (IBM
334 Corporation Software Group, Somers, NY).

335

336 **3. Results**

337 The temporal trends of SWC and Tsoil varied significantly between species with Silver fir
338 stands showing higher SWC and lower Tsoil, although no such significant trend was found
339 for R_s (Figs. 1 and S2). When differences in SWC, Tsoil and R_s were modeled considering
340 tree status (living or dead), living trees differed significantly from the dead ones only when
341 SWC and R_s were considered. Specifically, dead trees showed higher SWC and R_s values
342 than the living ones (Fig. 1, Fig. S3). Nevertheless, no differences between species were
343 found (Fig. S3).

344

345 Overall, R_s was consistently higher under dead trees with respect to living ones (Fig. 2, Table
346 S1). According to our results, CO₂ emissions under dead trees were on average 21% higher
347 than under living ones. On the other hand, R_H , specific root length/area (SRL/SRA), total
348 organic C and N (TOC and TON), and soil moisture (SWC) were among the environmental
349 variables that were consistently higher, although not always significantly, under dead trees
350 comparing with the living ones, being thus positively affected by tree mortality (Fig. 2, Table
351 S1). Other variables such as pH, C:N ratio, or total fine root biomass/volume (FRB and FRV,
352 respectively) showed less sensitivity to tree mortality and/or less consistent trends across tree
353 species, although FRB tend to be lower under dead trees (Fig. 2, Table S1). No clear trends
354 in differences in successional vegetation (Grass and understory cover) or tree competition
355 were found between living and dead trees (Table S1). This was because most sites had

356 already a dense cover of understory of broadleaf seedlings and grasses (Table 1)
357 independently on the health status of individual trees.

358

359 Both mean soil temperature and nutrient availability (PC2) were, together with tree status
360 (living vs death) the two environmental variables that better explained variability of R_s across
361 sites (Fig. 3, Table S1). As expected for ecosystems generally limited by temperature, T_{soil}
362 explained a large portion of across-site variability in R_s (Fig. 3, Table SXX), whereas R_s was
363 also strongly driven by nutrient availability (PC2, Fig. 3, Table SXX). Across-sites variability
364 in R_s was also strongly determined by tree health status, as observed in Fig. 1 and S2 (Fig.
365 3). Whereas the model was “forced” to include tree status as a fixed variable (we kept “status”
366 as a fixed variable to graphically show R_H rates for both, soils collected under dead and living
367 trees) no differences in R_H between soil collected under dead and living trees were found
368 (Figure 4). On the other hand, we found a strong effect of the nutritional status (PC1) and the
369 quantity of SOM (PC2) on R_H (Fig. 4, Table S2). Additionally, the best obtained model also
370 includes a significant negative effect of SRL over R_H (Fig. 4, Table S2).

371

372 Structural equation models (SEMs) were designed to test the direct and indirect influence of
373 both biotic and abiotic factors on R_s and R_H . SEM shows the complex causal-effect cascade
374 of processes controlling R_s and R_H (Fig. 5). SEM shows how strongly forest structure (tree
375 size and density, understory and grass cover) determines, directly or indirectly, the observed
376 variability of soil abiotic (microclimate, pH, nutrient content) and biotic (SRL, FRV, R_H)
377 environmental variables, resulting in the observed variability in R_s across sites (Fig. 5). Both,
378 trees (i.e. size and tree density) and understory cover exerted a strong effect over soil
379 microclimate (T_{soil}), soil pH and nutrients (PCA). Whereas conifers tend to acidify soils, we

380 here observe how an increasing cover of broadleaf understory was associated with increases
381 in pH, which, on the other hand, is behind observed improvement of soil nutritional status
382 (PC1) and SOM (PC2). The presence of grasses was also directly associated with increase in
383 SOM (PC2), decrease in FRV but increase in SRA (Fig. 5). As observed in Fig. 3 and 4,
384 Tsoil, and both axes of the PCA determined rates of R_s , but multigroup SEM shows a tighter
385 control of Tsoil over R_s under dead than under living trees, as illustrated by the significantly
386 higher ML coefficient obtained (Fig. 5). Multigroup SEM also shows how conifers and
387 successional vegetation exerted an opposite effect over the demography of fine roots (SRL
388 and FRV) (Fig. 5). Living conifers exerted an overall negative effect over SRL, whereas the
389 presence of grasses was positively associated with SRL (Fig. 5). On the other hand, the total
390 fine root volume (FRV) was stimulated in poor soils (high PC1) and high SOM contents (low
391 PC2). The presence of grasses and an increasing cover of broadleaf understory was also
392 negatively associated with FRV. We here show how, independently of the health status of
393 the conifers, increase in the specific root area of fine roots affected negatively to R_H (Fig. 5).
394 Controls of R_H were also different depending on the conifer health status (living or dead)
395 (Fig. 5). While living, conifers exert a positive control over R_H , when conifers die, variability
396 of R_H was mainly controlled by nutrient status (PC1) and SOM (PC2) (besides SRL). Finally,
397 observed variability of R_H seems to be more related to variability of R_s under dead than under
398 living conifers, where no relation at all between both fluxes was found (Fig. 5).

399

400 **4. Discussion**

401 We here reported large events of drought-induced mortality on stands dominated by three of
402 the conifer tree species most widely distributed in the Carpathian mountain range (Table 1).
403 This drought-induced mortality coincides with globally increasing reported events of conifer

404 decline, which is being generally attributed to historical management practices, e.g.
405 favoring/planting conifer species outside their climatic and structural optimum (e.g. Barberó,
406 Loissell, Quezel, Richardson & Romane 1998; Urbietta et al., 2008; Ruiz-Benito et al., 2012),
407 or to the fact that climate-change induced increases in temperature and intense droughts are
408 generally affecting more to conifer-like than to angiosperms-like related functional traits
409 (Henne Paul et al., 2015; McIntyre et al., 2015; Ruiz-Benito et al., 2017). Indeed, the
410 observed increasing presence of an understory vegetation of seedlings mainly composed by
411 native broadleaf species (e.g. *Fagus sylvatica*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Fraxinus ornus*, *Acer*
412 *campestre*, *Quercus petraea*, *Ulmus glabra*) (Table 1) coincides with these global
413 observations and are, therefore, in accordance with this general decline in conifer dominance,
414 especially ubiquitously observed in European forests.

415

416 *4.1 Cascading effects stimulating soil CO₂ emissions*

417 Drought induced conifer mortality resulted in large increases in biogenic soil CO₂ emissions
418 (R_s) averaging 21% increase with respect to R_s under living trees and persisting during two
419 consecutive years (2016-2017), four to five years after the mortality event occurred in 2012.
420 Given the observed large proportion of tree mortality after the 2012 drought (Table 1), this
421 enduring and dominating tree mortality-induced hot-spot of CO₂ might be responsible for
422 decelerating the capacity of these ecosystems to recover pre-mortality levels of C
423 sequestration (e.g. Moore et al, 2013). Our results are not in accordance with decreases in R_s
424 observed under experimental tree girdling manipulations (e.g. Högberg et al., 2001; Binkley
425 et al., 2006; Nave et al., 2011; Levy-Varon et al., 2014) or observed under natural conditions,
426 as in massive tree mortality events caused by bark beetle attacks (e.g. Moore et al. 2013) or

427 infections by pathogens, e.g. *Phytophthora cinammoni* (Avila et al., 2016). Literature shows
428 how tree death results in an almost immediate and dramatic decrease in rates of R_s from the
429 decrease in the supply of newly plants-fixed carbohydrate for autotrophic respiration (R_{root}),
430 mycorrhiza activity and rhizosphere heterotrophic respiration (Subke et al., 2004; Högberg
431 et al., 2007). This drop in R_s associated with tree mortality may last for decades in
432 monospecific forest (e.g. Moore et al. 2013, Avila et al., 2016), while other studies have
433 shown how depending on the level of the perturbation and the secondary successional
434 processes, R_s may recover pre-perturbation values after several years (e.g. Levy-Varon et al.,
435 2014; Barba et al., 2016) or even increase during favorable seasons in mixed forest (Barba et
436 al., 2013). Hence, to the initial physiological collapse that tree mortality produces in a system,
437 ecosystem functional recover, and particularly R_s , depends on the degree of perturbation but
438 also on the process of secondary succession triggered by tree mortality (Levy-Varon et al.,
439 2014; Lloret et al., 2015; Barba et al., 2018).

440

441 In these conifer forests so representative for the Carpathians' landscape, the observed hot-
442 spot of CO_2 under dead trees was strongly dominated by heterotrophic activity (R_H) (Fig. 2
443 and 5). We here postulate that these mortality-triggered hot-spots of R_H and R_s were mostly
444 explained by an increase in the quality and quantity of SOM associated with both the increase
445 in senescent material and the successional process following tree death (Fig. 2, 4 and 5). The
446 observed increase in topsoil SOM (PC2, TOC) under dead trees (Figure 2) could be
447 attributed, at least partially, to the accumulation of senescent plant material (leaves, roots and
448 branches) which generally accumulates under dead trees and results in a substantial increase
449 in SOM (Moore et al. 2013). However, SOM accumulation under dead conifers alone cannot

450 explain the observed increase in R_H because, and, as observed R_H was very sensitive to
451 increase in soil nutrient availability (Figure 4, Table S3).

452

453 Besides, we here observed how shifts in the controls of R_s after the massive mortality event
454 of 2012 ultimately resulted in a stronger dominant role of successional vegetation (broadleaf
455 seedlings, shrubland and grasses) in controlling those belowground environmental factors
456 directly or indirectly affecting biotic soil fluxes (R_s and R_H) (Figure 5). This shift towards
457 greater understory control over soil functioning in detriment of the control exerted by the
458 conifers while they were alive influenced microclimate (SWC and T_{soil}), abiotic soil
459 environment (pH), nutrient quality (PC1) and quantity (PC2) or fine root demography
460 (SRA/SRL, FRV) (Figs. 2, 3, 4 and 5). (Fig. 5a). These changes were further reflected in
461 change in the magnitude and biotic soil fluxes (R_s and R_H)

462

463 For instance, the increase in pH and grassland cover from shift in aboveground vegetation
464 dominance was also playing a critical role in increasing SOM (Fig. 5). This is because under
465 conifer influence, the generally low soil pH and low quality of the residues from the high
466 proportion of recalcitrant compounds, e.g. lignin's, and or allelopathic molecules (e.g. Curiel
467 Yuste et al. 2005; Fernández-Alonso et al., 2018) slows down the breakdown of litter and its
468 incorporation to SOM in the mineral soil. On the other hand, incorporation of litter in SOM
469 occurs generally faster in ecosystems dominated by broadleaf species because the generally
470 higher pH and higher palatability of the produced residues stimulates bioturbation (Frouz et
471 al., 2009). Indeed, the multigroup SEM further shows how the increase in pH associated with
472 the increasing presence of understory vegetation had a direct and strong positive effect over
473 SOM quality (PC1), suggesting that on top of the increase in SOM under dead trees, the

474 secondary successional processes triggered by conifer mortality was positively affecting the
475 quality of the substrate. Our results, therefore, clearly indicate how the shift in vegetation
476 dominance associated with conifer mortality had a strong impact over the quantity and quality
477 of SOM, resulting in increased heterotrophic activity, which subsequently affected R_s .

478

479 Results, hence, evidenced how cascading mechanisms triggered by selective tree mortality
480 and the subsequent secondary successional processes may play a critical role in regulating
481 soil functioning and soil CO_2 emissions during transitional states (Barba et al., 2013; Barba
482 et al., 2016; Fernández-Alonso et al., 2018); Garcia-Angulo et al., in prep.).

483

484 *4.2 Cascading effects suppressing soil CO_2 emissions*

485 Other key tree mortality-induced cascading effect had also strong, negative impacts over this
486 heterotrophic source of CO_2 . For instance, the observed shift towards a resource-acquisitive
487 strategy under dead trees, reflected in an increase in the fine roots specific root length/area
488 (SRL/SRA) (Eissenstat et al., 2000), was mainly associated with an increase in the presence
489 of grasses (Fig. 5). This shift in resource-acquisitive strategy under dead trees suggest that
490 the belowground niche left by death conifers creates an opportunity to the surrounding early
491 successional vegetation to obtain resources (nutrients and moisture) (Curiel Yuste et al.,
492 2012; Barba et al., 2013) whose acquisition is, otherwise, subjected to strong competition,
493 especially in nutrient-poor, low pH conifer sites as such (Table 2). Indeed, the multigroup
494 SEM shows how the poor nutrient conditions under conifers (PC1), while alive, promoted a
495 bigger radical system (higher FRV) but with relatively less very fine roots (suppressing SRL).
496 The substantial increase in the surface of absorption of the radical system associated with
497 tree mortality (increase in SRL and SRA; Fig. 2) responded to a shift towards a fine-root

498 demography optimized by maximization of nutrients acquisition and specially dominated by
499 early successional grass species (Fig. 5) (Roumet et al., 2016).

500

501 Given the generally observed linear relation between SRL and, on one hand, fine roots
502 turnover rates (Silver and Miya, 2001; Hobbie et al., 2010; Roumet et al., 2016) and, on the
503 other hand, rates of root respiration, R_A (Reich Peter et al., 2008; Makita et al., 2012; Picon-
504 Cochard et al., 2012), this shift towards a resource acquisitive strategy was expected to be
505 positively associated with R_s and R_H . However, and on the contrary, we here observed a very
506 consistent negative relation between this increase in fine root adsorption capacity and R_H
507 suggesting that this shift in fine-root demography was actually suppressing heterotrophic
508 activity (negative priming; Kuzyakov 2002) rather than stimulating it. Indeed, an increase in
509 competition for key nutrients (e.g. N, P, K), which could be maximal in this low pH soils
510 where nutrients are generally limiting soil biogenic activity, can suppress microbial biomass
511 and metabolisms, thereby suppressing R_H (e.g. Schimel, Jackson and Firestone 1989; Wang
512 & Bakken 1997; Kuzyakov 2002). This observed R_H suppression, hence, shows how
513 successional vegetation around death conifers may have the ability to gradually outcompete
514 soil heterotrophs in the competition for resources, which at the medium term may further
515 suppress present uncontrolled heterotrophic source of CO_2 .

516

517 **5. Conclusions**

518 We here collected compelling evidences on mechanisms of above-belowground feedbacks
519 triggered by tree mortality ultimately leading to strong impacts on soil functioning (increase
520 in soil CO_2 emissions). Ecosystem recover after conifer mortality and subsequent gradual
521 process of secondary succession by an understory of grasses and autochthonous broadleaf

522 species resulted in an average increment of biogenic emissions of 21%, 4-5 years after the
523 large mortality event of 2012. Tree mortality was responsible for transitional states during
524 which heterotrophic activity (R_H) was favored by the increase in senescent material, but also
525 by changes in the soil microenvironment favoring heterotrophic activity (e.g. climate, pH and
526 SOM). We also show how early successional vegetation around death conifers (mainly
527 grasses) have gradually developed the ability to outcompete soil heterotrophs in the
528 competition for resources, which negatively affects the magnitude of the hot-spot of R_H
529 activity. Our results, hence, call the attention to the relevance of understanding ecological
530 responses to tree mortality and its effect on above-belowground feedbacks that may
531 substantially determine dynamics of key biogeochemical cycles (e.g. C and N) at local and
532 regional scales. Our results further highlight the importance of applying integrative
533 ecological visions in order to understand and being able to predict responses and variability
534 of R_s , especially in a changing world where episodes of forest defoliation and die-off
535 associated with climate change are substantially incrementing.

536

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549

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712

713 **Fig. captions**

714

715 **Fig. 1.** Evolution of soil moisture (SWC), soil temperature (T_{soil}) and soil respiration (R_s)
716 as a function of time and conifer health status (living or dead). Error bars represent the
717 standard error of the mean.

718

719 **Fig. 2.** Relative changes in soil abiotic (microclimate, pH) and biotic (fine root demography,
720 R_s , R_H) as well as soil total organic carbon and total organic nitrogen (TOC and TON,
721 respectively). Positive values (right hand side of the vertical bar) represents an increase that
722 particular variable under dead with respect to under living conifers. Error bars represent
723 standard error of the mean.

724

725 **Fig. 3.** Linear mixed-effects models for soil respiration (R_s). Solid line represents modeled
726 R_s responses under dead trees, whereas dotted lines represent the same under living trees.
727 T_s = soil temperature at 5 cm depth; PC2= Second dimension of the PCA conducted to reduce
728 the n-dimensional of soil nutrients.

729

730 **Fig. 4.** Linear mixed-effects models for heterotrophic respiration (R_H). Solid line represents
731 modeled R_s responses under dead trees, whereas dotted lines represent the same under living
732 trees. SRL= Specific root length; PC1= Second dimension of the PCA conducted to reduce
733 the n-dimensional of soil nutrients; PC2= Second dimension of the PCA conducted to reduce
734 the n-dimensional of soil nutrients.

735

736 **Fig. 5.** Multigroup SEM representation. Path diagrams representing hypothesized causal
737 relationships among aboveground vegetation, biotic and abiotic variables, soil respiration
738 (R_s) and soil heterotrophic activity (R_H) under living (a) and dead (b) conifers. Arrows depict
739 causal relationships: positive and negative effects are indicated by solid and dashed lines
740 respectively, with numbers indicating standardized estimated regression weights (SRW).
741 Arrow widths are proportional to significance values according to the legend. Paths with
742 coefficients non-significant are in gray. Colored coefficients represent those causal
743 relationships where the strength of the relation differed between soils under living (green)
744 and under dead (orange) trees.

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				Mort	Alt	SL	OR	MAP	MAT	DBH	Height	CAP	Age	LAI		UC	GC
site	species	Coordinates	Soil Type	%	m.a.s.l.	Deg	Deg	mm	°C	cm	m	m ²	y	m ² /m ²	%	%	
DIMBU MORII	AA	Lat 45.58 Long 25.63	Eutricambisol	21	825	37	234	593	6.4	55	28	32	147	3.5	23 (7Fs3Aa)	18	
KRONSTADT	AA	Lat 45.58 Long 25.60	Eutricambisol	23	945	37	213	593	6.4	50	30	23	149	3.6	20 (9Fs1Aa)	53	
RASNOV	AA	Lat 45.49 Long 25.43	Eutricambisol litic	19	1250	37	213	693	3.7	54	30	30	145	3.6	8 (6Fs3Pa1Aa)	34	
LEMPES	PN	Lat 45.72 Long 25.64	Eutricambisol	27	561	17	225	593	6.4	39	23	27	99	3.4	41 (2Tc2Fs3Ap1Ug1Ac1Fo)	19	
RACADAU	PN	Lat 45.63 Long 25.60	Leptosol	16	753	30	121	593	6.4	43	24	28	96	4.3	69 (5Fo3Ug1Tc1Ac)	9	
SCHEI	PN	Lat 45.63 Long 25.57	Litic rendzina	18	456	36	117	593	6.4	45	25	30	97	3.8	55 (2Tc1Ac1Ug1Cb3Ap2Fs1Fo)	10	
LEMPES	PS	Lat 45.73 Long 25.64	Eutricambisol	22	545	24	115	593	6.4	37	19	20	111	2.7	68 (9Fe1Ug)	73	
CODLEA	PS	Lat 45.70 Long 24.43	Eutricambisol	18	712	18	139	599	6.6	45	24	21	115	3.3	37 (2Ap4Cb1Ug2Ac1Fs)	29	
TELIU	PS	Lat 45.70 Long 25.86	Regosol	17	606	33	190	601	5.6	40	25	28	114	3.9	7 (2Fs4Cb1Ac2Qp1Ps)	4	

Table 1. Location, identity of the dominant conifer and structural characteristics of the 9 different sites under study. Mort= Mortality rate (%); Alt= Site Altitude (m); SL = Slope (°); OR= Orientation (°); MAP= mean annual precipitation (mm); MAT= mean annual temperature (°C); DBH =diameter of breast height (cm), CAP= canopy area (m²); LAI- leaf area index, UC= Understorey cover(%), GC = Grassland cover (%); Understorey cover= (Fs-*Fagus sylvatica*, Fo-*Fraxinus ornis*, Fe-*Fraxinus excelsior*, Pa-*Picea abies*, Cb-*Carpinus betulus*, Ug-*Ulmus glabra*, Ac-*Acer campestre*, Tc-*Tilia cordata*, Ap-*Acer platanoides* and *Acer pseudoplatanus*, Qp-*Quercus petraea*, Ps-*Pinus sylvestris*, Aa-*Abies alba*)